

Effect of a Nucleating Agent on Crystallization Behavior and Mechanical property of PLA stereocomplex

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Introduction

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), linear aliphatic biodegradable polyester derived from biomass through bioconversion and polymerization has become a potential candidate for various large-scale industrial applications in the areas of automotive, biomedical, etc. Although PLA has an advantage on environmental protection and renewable resources, there is a critical issue concerning the crystallization rate and heat resistance of molded articles [1].

The most viable method to increase the overall crystallization rate was the blending of nucleating agent [2]. Relatively few studies had focused on the nucleating agents for PLA. In this article, two kind of nucleating agents were blended with industrial produced PLA whose crystallinity was very low.

Poly lactide, polyester derived from renewable resources, can be synthesized using either L-lactide or D-lactide. Interestingly, in the 1980s, it was found that an equivalent mixture of PLLA and PDLA formed a stereocomplex [3,4]. The stereocomplex has a melting temperature ($T_m=230^\circ\text{C}$) that is approximately 50°C higher than the T_m of either PLLA or PDLA [5]. This significant increase in melting temperature is due to the strong van der Waals interactions in the stereocomplex crystalline structure [6,7,8]. stereocomplexation enhances the mechanical properties, the thermal-resistance, and the hydrolysis-resistance of PLA based materials [9, 10, 11].

In this study, we tried to blend PLLA and PDLA at 92:8, 75:25 compositions to form PLA stereocomplexes. Two kind of PDLA amounts are added in PLLA and stereocomplex crystallites is produced in the PLLA matrix. In addition, PLLA M/B (grade: 3801X, Talc 12 wt%) and Talc was added to enhance crystallization rate and mechanical property. Crystallization behavior thermal property and mechanical property of stereocomplexes were investigated by DSC, HDT, Izod impact tester, UTM.

Experimental

Materials

Poly (L-lactide), (PLLA, 4032D) and 3801X (PLLA M/B, Talc 12wt %) resins were used for the experimental work, and they were manufactured by Nature Works. Poly (D-lactide) (PDLA) was produced by SK Chemical Company. The melt indices (MI) for the resins of 4032D, 3801X and PDLA were 3, 8 and 8 g/10min (190°C , 2.16 kg). Talc (KCM-6300, Average particle size = $5.5\ \mu\text{m}$) sample were purchased from KOCH KOREA Company.

Preparation of blends

PLLA (4032D) and PDLA pellets were dried in a vacuum oven for 24h at 60°C . The PLLA(4032D)/PDLA blends with weight ratios of 100/0, 92/8, 75/25, 0/100 were prepared in a Twin screw extruder [BA-19(L/D=40, 19Φ , Co-rotating), BauTek, Korea]. And 3801X (PLLA M/B, Talc 12wt%) was diluted with PLLA and stereocomplex PLA(92/8, 75/25). Talc weight% of diluted 3801X was 1, 3, 5wt%. In case of dilution of 3801X with stereocomplex PLA was prepared using twin screw extruder (BA-19) in a one step. To compare with 3801X, Talc was incorporated at 5wt% amount in the PLLA and stereocomplex PLA (92/8, 75/25).

The temperature profile along the extruder barrel was $200\text{-}230^\circ\text{C}$, and the temperature at the die was 220°C . The screw speed was 200 rpm. The recipes of composites are showed in Table 1.

Characterization

The phase structure of the blends was observed by field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). A JEOL Ltd. JSM-7500F scanning electron microscope was used for measurements at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. All of the samples were fractured by immersion in liquid nitrogen for about 10 min. The fractured surface was then coated with a thin layer of gold before the observation.

Table1. Compounding recipes of PLLA/PDLA blends with nucleating agents

Grade	PLLA (wt%)	PDLA (wt%)	3801X (wt%)	Talc (wt%)
PLLA100	100	0	-	-
PL92D8	92	8	-	-
PL75D25	75	25	-	-
PLLA95_T5	95	-	-	5
PL100_3801X(T1)	91.7	-	8.3	-
PL100_3801X(T3)	75	-	25	-
PL100_3801X(T5)	58.3	-	41.7	-
PL92D8_T5	87.4	4.6	-	5
PL92D8_3801X(T1)	83.7	8	8.3	-
PL92D8_3801X(T3)	67	8	25	-
PL92D8_3801X(T5)	50.6	8	41.4	-
PL75D25_T5	71.3	23.7	-	5
PL75D25_3801X(T1)	66.7	25	8.3	-
PL75D25_3801X(T3)	50	25	25	-
PL75D25_3801X(T5)	33.6	25	41.4	-

Thermal properties were analyzed with Perkin-Elmer Pyris Diamond differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) calibrated with indium as standard. The specimens were heated from 0 to 250 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min, followed by an isothermal at 250 °C for 2min, and a subsequent cooling scan to 0 °C at rate of 5 °C/min. And then were reheated to 250 °C at 10 °C/min.

Tiniusolsen 3-station heat distortion temperature test machine (Model303 HDTM) was used to measure the HDT values. The dimensions of the specimens were 130mm x 3.2mm x 13mm. They were carefully molded by a compression molding machine. HDT test were carried out according to ASTM D648. A load (0.455MPa) was applied directly to the mid-point of the test sample. The entire "station" was then submerged into a thermally controlled oil bath. The temperature of bath was increased at a rate of 2°C/min. Both applied load and elevated temperature would combinedly cause the test sample to deflect downward and the temperature at which it gave a deflection of 0.25 mm was subsequently taken as the HDT value.

Flexural and impact tests were carried out according to ASTM D790 and KS M 3055(notched, 3.2mm) test method. The Flexural modulus and strength tests were performed using a UTM (Tinius Olsen, H5KT). Span length was 100mm and the crosshead speed was set at 1.3mm/min. The impact strength test was analyzed by Izod impact strength tester (Sejin, SJTM-131) in room temperature.

Result and Discussion

Morphology

Figure 1a-1b shows the SEM micrographs of PLLA with nucleating agent. As you can see the talc size in the Figure 1, 3801X of Figure 1b is closer to the microtalc compared with that of Figure 1a. Size of talc can affect the mechanical properties when it is introduced into the polymer. As the size of Talc increases, a polymer such as PLLA become more ductile when nucleating agent is introduced into it. As a result, among its mechanical properties, flexural modulus will be increased and reduction of impact strength will be decreased.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. FE-SEM image of PLLA with nucleation agents. (a) Talc (b) 3801X

Crystallization

Table 2 presents the DSC results from the thermogram of the PLA stereocomplex composites at the first heating step. Also, Table 2 shows a melt crystallization temperature(T_{mc}) of the PLA stereocomplex composites at the cooling step. By comparing T_{mc} , it can be compared relatively crystallization rate of neat PLLA(4032D), SC PLA and SC PLA entered nucleating agents.

Figure 2 organized by DSC thermal properties and

thermogram data of neat PLLA(4032D), SC PLA and SC PLA introduced nucleating agents. Figure 2 shows that T_{mc} was significantly increased when nucleating agents were introduced to the PLLA using diluted 3801X(Talc 1wt%). But in the case of SC PLA(92/8, 75/25), T_{mc} was less increased. This result indicated that crystallization rate can be increased efficiently when nucleating agents were introduced to the PLLA. But SC PLA(75/25) entered nucleating agent has the greatest final absolute value in figure 2.

Table2. Thermal properties of PLLA/PDLA blends with nucleating agents

<i>Ist Scan</i>	T_g (°C)	T_m (°C)	T_{cc} (°C)	T_{mc} (°C) [ΔT_{mc}]
PLLA100	-	166	99	97-
PL100_3801X(T1)	60	167	95[4]	113[16]
PL100_3801X(T3)	59	167	93[6]	114[17]
PL100_3801X(T5)	55	165	81[12]	113[16]
PL92D8	58	167/218	103	98
PL92D8_3801X(T1)	61	167/216	93[10]	104[6]
PL92D8_3801X(T3)	56	165/216	79[14]	108[10]
PL92D8_3801X(T5)	54	164/216	78[1]	110[12]
PL75D25	61	167/217	92	99
PL75D25_3801X(T1)	59	166/216	85[7]	109[10]
PL75D25_3801X(T3)	55	165/216	83[9]	114[15]
PL75D25_3801X(T5)	55	164/215	73[19]	114[15]

Fig. 2. Melt crystallization temperature of PLLA and SC PLA with nucleating agents.

Thermal property

Figure 3 presents heat distortion temperature(HDT) analysis data of PLA stereocomplex by heat distortion tester. According to the Figure 3, compared with neat PLLA, stereocomplex PLA has much more increased HDT value. HDT value is not dramatically changed as the

amount of the PDLA is changed. Nucleating agent affects more the rise in the HDT value than stereocomplex forming. When nucleating agent is added into stereocomplex, the HDT value is just a little increased and that shows stereocomplex has less impact on HDT value than nucleating agent.

Fig. 3. Heat Deflection Temperature of PLLA and SC PLA with nucleating agents

Mechanical property

Figure 4 presents the mechanical property of PLLA and SC PLA. The mechanical property of homopolymer PLLA is greater than PLA stereocomplex polymer. You can see the same tendency in the figure 5. When nucleating agent is added into pure PLLA and its stereocomplex type polymer, the properties of pure PLLA is improved more than its stereocomplex type polymer. The blend with talc comparatively has higher flexural modulus and less reduction of the impact strength than microtalc.

Fig. 4. Mechanical property of PLLA and SC PLA

Figure 5 presents the mechanical property of PLLA and SC PLA entered nucleating agents. Figure 5 shows

that mechanical property of PLLA with diluted 3801X had highest value compared with another. In particular, Impact strength of SC PLA with nucleating agents was dramatically reduced in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Mechanical property of PLLA and SC PLA with nucleating agents.

Conclusion

Crystallization rate was increased when nucleating agents such as diluted 3801X (Talc wt% =1, 3, 5) and Talc was introduced in PLLA, SC PLA. Crystallization rate can be increased efficiently when diluted 3801X were introduced to the PLLA compared with SC PLA. Increasing the amount of PDLA, melt crystallization temperature was increased.

According to the HDT result, compared with neat PLLA, stereocomplex PLA has much more increased HDT value. In this result, nucleating agent affects more on the increasing HDT value than stereocomplexation. When nucleating agent is added into stereocomplex, the HDT value is just a little increased.

Mechanical results show that the mechanical property of homopolymer PLLA is greater than PLA stereocomplex polymer. And the blend with talc comparatively has higher flexural modulus and less reduction of impact strength than microtalc. Therefore, Mechanical property of PLLA with diluted 3801X had highest value compared with another.

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